

METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING INSTRUMENT ENSEMBLES IN SPECIALIZED CULTURE AND ART SCHOOLS

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of music in human life, musical instruments, requirements for music teachers, attention and demand for music in ancient times and today. Also, scientific discussions are held about the methodology of organizing musical ensembles in specialized culture and art schools.

Key words: music, musical instrument, singer, accompanist, music teacher, pedagogy, musical ensemble.

Introduction.

Uzbek folk instruments have been developed over centuries, with colorful, original instruments suitable for all branches of music. If we look at the past, among our thinkers al-Farabi in his "Big Book of Music", Safiuddin Urmawi in his musical treatise, Ahmadi in his "Discussion of Words", Zaynul al-Din Husayni in his treatise "Risola dar bayani va amalik muzik", Abdurrahman Jami in his "Music Treatise" " who studied musical instruments and described various aspects of research issues in their works. Speaking about the music industry, our respected president said: "You know, a person who is close to culture has a cultured outlook. His life will be long. 10 million is bringing investment in every big enterprise. But, is it possible to make one musical ensemble with an investment of 10 million? Is it possible to make one maqam ensemble? Make Saturday a day for singing there. With song, you will be blessed 10 times in your work. With culture, you will start new plans 10 times in that company. Love appears on a person's face."

A separate chapter of the Concept of Music Education in Secondary Schools of the Republic of Uzbekistan is devoted to the set of modern music teachers and their professional qualities. The document states: "The modern music teacher should be highly cultured, have unlimited devotion to his profession, and possess advanced pedagogical thinking." He must have the capacity for continuous professional and cultural development. He needs to have comprehensive knowledge and skills in the fields of music, aesthetics, pedagogy and psychology-physiology, in particular, music teaching methodology. Especially in the profession of a music teacher, it is necessary to embody the qualities of playing instruments, singing, choir conducting and music theory. Today's music teacher is a scientific thinker, a master of advanced experiences, inquisitive and creative, and should strive to discover new forms and methods of music education. It is necessary to connect and enrich the content of music education with the content of other subjects and everyday life. The advanced experience and new methods discovered by the inquisitive and creative teacher are the main support and source of inspiration for the continuous improvement and development of music education in the school. A knowledgeable and experienced music teacher, as an art intellectual, is the leader of musical and educational work in the school."

In fact, the field of music and the performance of musical instruments is one of the most important issues today. Music education is distinguished from other subjects by a number of its features. For example, it requires a combination of qualifications, skills and knowledge of several professional activities (musical art). Even if it is considered in the direction of ordinary art, not every musician-artist can conduct music lessons in school. In order to conduct lessons in music at the level of the new program and the requirements of the state education standards, the teacher must first of all learn pedagogy, psychology, child and youth physiology, ethics and aesthetics theory, music theory (*elementary theory of music, analysis of musical works, harmony, solfeggio, music education 'teaching methodology'*) should have the necessary knowledge and skills in the practical fields of music (*vocal singing, conducting, playing instruments*), directing, acting, dance art. That is, a music teacher has to act as an instrumentalist, singer, choir conductor, accompanist, music theorist and stylist, skilled organizer, and screenwriter during a single lesson.

There are many types of musical instruments. If we give an example of these, they include the qaryok, sibizga, chanqovuz, drum, bulomon, qaryok, safoil, chindovul, sagat, trumpet, trumpet, dombira and other musical instruments. The musical instruments listed above have been performed by our people at weddings, parties, and celebrations since ancient times and have survived to this day. In addition, Uzbek folk instruments are divided into five groups:

- ❖ *A group of wind instruments*
- ❖ *A group of stringed percussion instruments*
- ❖ *A group of mezrobli instruments*
- ❖ *A group of percussion instruments*
- ❖ *Band of bowed instruments*

These groups include several musical instruments. There are many types of them. Information about the definition of musical instruments, i.e., their forms, structures, structural aspects, and performers began to be covered in fiction literature and musical treatises, mainly since the Middle Ages. It's no secret to all of us how much the Uzbek people touched on the national instruments in the works of our great masters. That is why it is not an exaggeration to say that it is our sacred duty to the Uzbek people to teach and leave our folk instruments, which have been handed down to us since ancient times and are another reason for the preservation of our nationality, as a legacy to the next generation. For this, it is necessary to start education and upbringing of our children from a young age. One of the main tasks is to train mature personnel in education and upbringing of the young generation. If we use the most advanced pedagogical technologies to provide high-quality lessons to students in schools, we would have fulfilled one of the great tasks set before us. A music teacher needs an independent and creative approach to each lesson. His creativity is such that he also works as a scriptwriter, performer and director of a one-hour class. That's why music class is also called art class. The role of a music teacher in school life is broad and multifaceted. Organization and management of extracurricular music lessons, public forms of music education at school (*meetings, holidays, lectures, concerts, preparation and participation in auditions, "Alifbe" holidays, music weeks, etc.*) are the duties of the teacher. At the same time, he is in constant contact with non-school educational institutions (*children's music schools, student creative centers, children's theaters, choral etudes, etc.*), attracting talented, musically talented students to them and learning from their activities in school life. In turn, the work of

using music places responsible tasks on the music teacher. The State Educational Standard and Curriculum for the subject of music requires teachers working in general schools to update the content of their educational and educational work and the working methods they use. Also, it is necessary to approach the professional training of future teachers in the musical-pedagogical education faculties of the higher education system focused on the training of music teachers from the point of view of these requirements. These requirements are widely covered in textbooks, manuals, recommendations, educational and methodological literature. Another distinctive feature of the music curriculum is that it is necessary to develop musical literacy, which is the basis of the subject of "musical culture" of secondary schools, a number of musical laws, including musical speech, the means of expression of music, forms of music, the structure and development of music, modernity of music, etc. should be thoroughly studied. Therefore, in order to teach in the content of music science programs, a music teacher must constantly improve his musical-theoretical knowledge. Because the issues of artistic and aesthetic education, which is an important component of raising the young generation growing up in our country with a stable interest and love for our motherland, our nation and our national values, i.e. making a person morally and educationally perfect The great responsibility placed by the society and our state in solving the issues of personal education makes the music teacher an urgent task.

The position of music education and teachers is very high and extremely responsible in ensuring the effectiveness of music education and upbringing, in awakening the interest of students and young people in the art of music and life through it. Based on what has been said, it is correct to explain the content of the work of music teachers according to the programs developed on the new national basis as follows: The teacher should effectively organize the educational process of music in secondary schools. and in order to ensure its effectiveness, to form the musical culture of students and young people in every way, to make them aware of various fields of musical art, to consciously perceive music, to be able to express their ideas, to understand and appreciate the simplest musical laws it is necessary to educate students to be able to give, to develop the skills of working on themselves in order to strengthen their knowledge of music, and to organize the educational process based on this. Pedagogical skills of a music teacher. The personality of the music teacher occupies a special place in the mental and moral development of students. He should have a broad outlook, a pure heart, a sweet talker, and a child. Such qualities cannot be cultivated in any person. Pedagogical skill or art is an intangible process that can be carried out with understanding, research, experiences, many daily activities, moments spent with children. It is a combination of scientific knowledge, ability to solve educational problems, attention to the personality of the child, developed imagination, etc. Pedagogical skill in the creative activity of a modern music teacher is clearly manifested in the following:

- searching for new methods and tools in music education, skillfully connecting them with traditional methods;
- being able to show and teach the connection between life and the art of music;
- conveying the content and meaning of music to children, making interdisciplinary communication;
- in the music teacher's constant work on himself and creative search.

The high professional training of the teacher is of great importance in the improvement of music lessons and in realizing the educational potential of the art of music.

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